

The Solvation of Cations in Nonaqueous Solvents from the Effect of Solvent Change on the Potential of Clay Membrane Electrode

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The change in the value of "mobility ratio" and hence of the standard electrode potential E° in solution was measured with variation of mole fraction of water in a mixture of ethanol/water, methanol/water and glycol/water by using clay membrane electrode which separates two solutions of the same K^+ activity but different water activity. By suitable extrapolation in the change in E° in solution from 100% water to 100% ethanol, methanol and glycol was estimated. The respective values of free energy change for change of solvent relative to H^+ were -0.92 and $+0.25$ Kcal. for the ethanol and methanol systems but practically zero for the glycol system. From this relative free energy change, absolute free energy change with change in medium was evaluated and were found to be -6.32 and -5.55 Kcal for ethanol and methanol and by using Born equation the solvated ionic radius of K^+ in these nonaqueous solvents was calculated. The solvated ionic radii of K^+ in ethanol and methanol were found to be 13.45 \AA and 9.98 \AA respectively. With glycol apparently no change in hydrated K^+ ion radius takes place, suggesting that glycol owing to its large diameter is unable to replace the hydration layer around K^+ .

It was shown by Bose¹ that if a membrane is considered, in the limited range of validity of the Nernst equation, as a cation-reversible electrode, then the observed e.m.f. may be expressed as the difference between the e.m.f. of each element for a cell,

$$\left. \frac{aNa}{E_1} \right| \text{ Membrane } \left| \frac{aK}{E_2} \right. \text{ as } E = E_2 - E_1 = (E^\circ_K - E^\circ_{Na}) + 0.059 \log \frac{aNa}{aK} \text{ at } 25^\circ$$

If a membrane separates two solutions of same cation having the same activity but in different solvents, the e.m.f. will indicate the effect of solvent on the characteristic E° value of that cation which will give the free energy change of that ion in solution due to change of solvent by using the equation, $\Delta F^0 = -nE^0f$ where $f = \text{faraday}$, $n = 1$ for mono-valent cation. Using Born equation² which relates the standard free energy change with dielectric constant and ionic radii it is possible to evaluate the ionic radius of that cation in that particular solvent. For this, let us consider the cell set up of the type:—

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1. S. K. Bose, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1955, 3, 65.

2. M. Born, *E. Physik*, 1920, 1, 45.

$E = E^0_1 + E^0$; where E^0_1 = difference in standard electrode potentials of Ag, AgCl electrode in aqueous and nonaqueous media.

E^0 = difference in standard electrode potentials of K in aqueous and nonaqueous media,

E^0_1 can be obtained from the values of the previous workers^{3,4,5}. Hence from the observed value E of the cell, E^0 can be evaluated.

$$\text{Now } \Delta F = \frac{E^0 f}{4.2} \text{ calcs} \quad \dots (1)$$

for the cell reaction $K_a^+ + H_s^+ = H_a^+ + K_s^+$ where subscript 'a' stands for aqueous and 's' for solvated. The ΔF_H values for this reaction $H_s^+ \rightarrow H_a^+$ may be subtracted from ΔF , to get free energy change for the reaction $K_a^+ \rightarrow K_s^+$. This $\Delta F_{a \rightarrow s}$ can now be equated to Born eqn. by the relation at 25°.

$$-F_{a \rightarrow s} = \frac{Ne^2}{2 \times 4.2 \times 10^7} \left(\frac{1}{r_a \epsilon_a} - \frac{1}{r_s \epsilon_s} \right) \quad \dots (2)$$

or

$$-F_{a \rightarrow s} = \frac{6.06 \times 4.8 \times 4.8 \times 10^4}{2 \times 4.2} \left(\frac{1}{r_a \epsilon_a} - \frac{1}{r_s \epsilon_s} \right)$$

where r_a , r_s , ϵ_a , ϵ_s are ionic radii and dielectric constants in aquo and solvated media. From a knowledge of radius (r_a) of K^+ in aqueous medium and ϵ_s , ϵ_a dielectric constants of water and the nonaqueous medium, r_s , the radius of K^+ in the nonaqueous medium can be evaluated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Experimental procedure was similar to those mentioned earlier (Adhikari^{6,7}). After equilibrating the two sides of a membrane with respect to K^+ , these were tested for absence of asymmetry potential.

KCl solution of known K^+ activity in aqueous solvent was placed on one side of the membrane which separates a solution of same K^+ activity but in a mixture of the nonaqueous solvent with water. The whole set up was allowed to equilibrate in a thermostat at $25^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$; e.m.f. was measured after ensuring equilibrium using two similar Ag, AgCl electrodes having no asymmetry potential between them. Knowing the difference in standard electrode potentials for Ag, AgCl electrode in the two media (Feakins and French, *loc. cit.*) used, the E^0 value was evaluated in the manner indicated above. By varying the composition of the mixture, E^0 values corresponding to these solvent compositions were determined. The values of E^0 for different compositions of ethanol and water, methanol and water, glycol and water are given in Table I using Padegaon Ca- form and Aguagel Ca- form of the membranes which were heated to 600° for 48 hrs. (Cf. Adhikari⁷).

3. D. Feakins and C. M. French, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, Pt. II, 2581.
4. I. T. Oiwa, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1957, **61**, 1587.
5. G. J. Janz and H. Taniguchi, *Chem. Review*, 1953, **53**, 397.
6. M. Adhikari, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **40**, 373.
7. Idem., *ibid.*, 1961, **38**, 817.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

From Table I it will be noticed that the E^0 values for K^+ in glycol water system are close to zero at all compositions. It has been reported earlier that with glycol water mixture the mobility ratio between any cation pair is practically the same in glycol-water mixture as in water. In order to get E^0 for 100% ethanol and methanol it is necessary to have a plot of composition against E^0 . For this purpose, $\log E^0$ is plotted against $1/\log N_w$, where N_w = mole fraction of water.

TABLE I

Membrane used Padegaon Ca—form and Aquagel Ca—form; used Ag, AgCl electrode (outside +ve observed); P = Padegaon Ca—form, A = Aquagel Ca—form.

Solution and membrane, inside (Non aqueous solvent water mixture)/outside (water)	e.m.f. m.v. observed	E^0 Ag, AgCl between aqueous and non aqueous solvent water mixture	E^0 m.v.
a) <i>Aqueous-ethanolic solutions—</i>			
25% Ethanol, 75% water, Mole fraction of water = 0.89			
$\frac{.003K}{.033K}$ P	35.7	18.6	17.1
„ A	35.6	18.6	17.0
50% Ethanol, 50% water, Mole fraction of water = 0.72			
$\frac{.033K}{.003K}$ P	87.1	37.9	49.2
A	87.1	37.9	49.2
60% Ethanol, 40% water, Mol fraction of water = .63			
„ P	101.3	51.2	50.1
„ A	101.2	51.2	50.0
75% Ethanol, 25% water, Mole fraction of water = 0.46			
„ P	127.1	78.9	48.2
„ A	126.7	78.9	47.8
b) <i>Aquo-methanolic solutions</i>			
20% Methanol, 80% water, Mole fraction of water = 0.88			
$\frac{.083K}{.003K}$ P	23.5	13.6	9.9
„ A	23.6	13.6	10.9
50% Methanol, 50% water, Mole fraction of water = 0.64			
„ P	55.5	33.1	22.4
„ A	55.4	33.1	22.3

TABLE I (Contd.)

Solution and membrane, inside (Non aqueous solvent water mixture)/outside (water)	e.m.f.	E° Ag, AgCl between aqueous and non aqueous solvent water mixture	E° m.v.
60% Methanol, 40% water, Mole fraction of water = .54			
„ P	59.6	40.4	19.2
„ A	59.5	40.4	19.1
70% Methanol, 30% water, Mole fraction of water = 0.43			
„ P	72.1	56.9	15.2
„ A	72.0	56.9	15.1
c) <i>Aquo-glycolic solutions</i>			
20% Glycol, 80% water, Mole fraction of water = 0.93			
$\frac{-0.03K}{-0.03K}$ P	12.2	12.3	-0.1
„ A	12.3	12.3	0
30% Glycol, 70% water, Mole fraction of water = 0.89			
„ P	18.9	18.8	0.1
„ A	18.9	18.8	0.1
40% Glycol, 60% water, Mole fraction of water = 0.84			
$\frac{-0.03K}{-0.03K}$ P	25.3	25.2	0.1
„ A	25.3	25.2	0.1

TABLE 2

E° between water and non-aqueous solvent (by extrapolation of graph to $N_w = 0$)	Free energy change relative to H^+	Radius of hydrated K taken as	Calculated radius of K in Non aqueous solvent
Ethanol m.v. 39.8	-0.92	4.09Å	13.45Å
Methanol m.v. -11.2	+0.25	„	9.98Å
Glycol O m.v.	0	„	same as in water

Extrapolating these plots to $N_w = 0$ gives the value of E° for 100% ethanol and 100% methanol. These values are 39.8 m.v. and 11.2 m.v. respectively. From these E° 's the $\Delta F^\circ S$ have been calculated. Knowing ΔF_H , the solvation energy of H^{+17} and the solvated radius of K^+ in water, the solvated radius of this ion in ethanol and methanol is evaluated from equation 2. The solvated ionic radius, according to Eley and Evans⁸, is taken as that

8. D. D. Eley and M. G. Evans, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1938, **35**, 1093; Eley and Pepper, *ibid.*, 1941, **37**, 581.

of the ion with its co-ordination sphere (one molecular water layer) equal to $r = r_i + 2r_w$, where r_i = crystallographic ionic radius and equal to 1.33Å for K^+ (Conway⁹) and $2r_w$ = the diameter of water molecule which equals 2.76Å (Pauling¹⁰). On the basis of these considerations hydrated ionic radius of K^+ becomes 4.09Å . With this value for r_a and taking 24.30 and 32.63 the dielectric constants for ethanol and methanol at 25° respectively (Lange¹¹), equation 2 gives the values of r_s for K^+ in ethanol and methanol as 13.45Å and 9.98Å respectively. Because the difference in standard potential for K^+ in glycol and water is negligibly small, the free energy change for K^+ caused by change of medium is practically zero.

X-ray data indicate that K^+ forms substitutional solution in water, with most of the ions surrounded by four tetrahedrally oriented water molecules, so that the average radius of tetrahedral K^+ , $4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ion is 3.5Å (Brady and Krause¹²).

On this basis, that the effective solute species is K^+ , $4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with a radius of 3.5Å , the values of the ionic radius of K^+ in ethanol and methanol media calculated from equation 2, become 11.41Å and 8.51Å respectively.

If a similar model suggested by Eley and Evans (*loc. cit.*) of the hydrated ion is assumed in the case of ethanol and methanol media, the radii of K^+ would be as 5.33Å and 3.83Å , assuming the molecular diameter of ethanol and methanol to be 4.0Å and 2.5Å respectively¹³. The solvated radii of K^+ thus calculated are much lower than what have been estimated above. If the difference in the hydrated radius of K^+ from X-ray data and that given by Eley *et al.* is considered as due to contraction caused by electrostatic attraction between the solvent and the ion, the contraction coefficient is 0.85. Ethanol and methanol are water-like in structure and have dipole moments (vac.) of 1.70_D and 1.68_D respectively, slightly smaller than that for water, 1.85_D (Gurney¹⁴, Fessler and Strobel¹⁵). As a result of their larger sizes and lower bulk densities, ethanol and methanol have much smaller dielectric constants, namely 24.3 and 32.63 respectively compared to 78.54 for water, at 25° . If it is assumed that the same type of electrostatic attraction between K^+ and its surrounding solvent layer (e.g., ethanol and methanol) would prevail as is the case with K^+ in water, the contraction coefficient would be 0.85. That means, the actual radius of K^+ in ethanol and methanol on the Eley and Evans model and considering electrostatic contraction would be 4.53Å and 3.25Å respectively. These values are thus found to be much less than what we have estimated above. This shows that the solvation sheath around K^+ with these solvents cannot be explained with this model although ethanol and methanol are structurally similar

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10. L. Pauling, *The Nature of the Chemical Bonds.*, Chap. X, Cornell Univ., N.Y., 1948.
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13. Tables of Interatomic distances and configuration in molecules and ions. Published by the Chemical Society, London, 1958.
14. R. W. Gurney, *Ionic process in solution*, Mc Graw Hill Book., Co., N.Y., 1953, page 266.
15. R. G. Fessler and H. A. Strobel, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1963, **67**, 2562.

to water. Grunwald¹⁶ *et al.* from their study on the effect of solvent change on standard partial molar free energy for electrolytes using doxane-water mixture have shown that for small cations a purely coulombic model of cation solvent interaction could not accommodate the experimental facts and they developed a chemical model. On the basis of this, they explained that alkali cations are associated with about two dioxane molecules plus small but indeterminate number of water molecules. It is likely that a similar type of mixed solvent layer of ethanol, methanol with water exists around K^+ , which makes the calculation of solvated K^+ radius somewhat uncertain because the ion is surrounded by a spherical insulating layer of outer radius of arbitrary dielectric constant. Schug and Dedgar¹⁸ considered the actual free energy change for the change of solvent is the sum of a Born term and a term arising from specific ion solvent interaction viz., $\Delta F^0_1 = \Delta F_{\text{Born}} + \Delta F^0_{\text{spec}}$ and this ΔF^0_{spec} should be known to evaluate r_s using Born equation.

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17. B. Case and F. Parsond *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1967, **63**, 1224.
18. K. Schug and A. Dedger, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, **68**, 106.